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Impact Of Human And Artificial Intelligence Competencies On Customer Loyalty

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the impact of human and artificial intelligence (AI) competencies on customer loyalty, with responsiveness, empathy, communication and assurance as key determinants. The primary objective was to critically compare the competencies of both human and AI agents, and evaluate their respective impact on customer loyalty. A cross-sectional survey research design was adopted, utilizing a primary data collection approach. Given the infinite population of customers, the Cochran method was employed to determine a sample size of three hundred and sixty-nine customers, selected through a stratified sampling technique. The data were gathered through a four-point Likert scale questionnaire, which was administered on respondents via WhatsApp. The findings revealed that both human and AI competencies significantly impact customer loyalty, but with varying degrees of impact across different determinants. It was also found that human agents are more empathic than AI agents, leading to stronger customer loyalty, while AI system is more responsive than human agent. It was also revealed that AI excels in communication and human excels in assurance, leading to reliable responses. Based on the findings, the study recommended the optimization of human-AI collaboration in customer service., emphasizing the relevance of investing in AI, while training and retraining human on how to ensure responsive, emotion and solution driven interactions with customers.

Keywords: Human/Artificial Intelligence, responsiveness, communication, empathy, assurance.

INTRODUCTION

In the past, building sustainable business-customer relationships took human relations or interactions. Businesses invest huge amounts of time and resources in staff training on exceptional customer service, and customer complaints to build customer loyalty. The most successful relationship marketing-building strategies depend on customer-oriented personnel to make decisions and solve problems (Lamb et al., 2012). Human relations or interactions are a way businesses communicate with their customers. This communication takes different forms, such as verbal and nonverbal. When communicating, people may see other people's reactions and respond intentionally.

Today, with the advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI), the customer engagement landscape has undergone a significant transformation. It has changed the mode of relations in the business environment. According to Bhalerao et al. (2022), AI has changed the pattern of customer engagement and revolutionized how businesses engage their consumers. AI differs from human intuition because it is data-driven. Intuition is the most common approach used to determine the problem consumers face (Hawkins et al., 2001). AI only modifies the interplay between machines and humans in exceptional ways (Suraña and Aramendia, 2024).

To align with the current transformations, businesses are adopting artificial intelligence tools such as predictive analytics, machine learning, and natural language processing to stimulate and optimize customer engagement. Truly, AI is a relatively new technology with the potential to improve the impact on consumer behaviour (Rabby et al., 2021). By adopting AI algorithms, businesses analyze vast amounts of data to understand customers' needs, preferences, and behaviour. Ifekanandu et al. (2023) believed that this revolution would create a shift in decision-making from human to machine. Recently, customers believe that there is a loss of human touch with the adoption of AI in business. With the growing demand for AI, businesses are yet to find out how customers feel relating to AI instead of humans. Understanding the marketplace and customers is crucial. Even though AI brought about apparent benefits such as delivering personalized suggestions, rendering help and assistance, executing self-service tasks, quick response, and 24/7 service, there are negative sides to it.

Despite the importance of AI as it continues to reshape the business world, the questions in the mind of most people are: How do customers feel relating to AI, as against relating to humans? Can AI empathize with customers more than humans? Is human responsiveness faster than that of AI? Can AI communicate more effectively than humans in service interactions? Is AI-generated assurance in service delivery more impactful on customer loyalty than human-given assurance?

Pashine and Tripathi (2024) cautioned that less human interactions, if left unaddressed, would adversely affect consumer happiness. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to compare the impact of human competence on customer loyalty with the impact of AI competence on customer loyalty using responsiveness, empathy, communication, and assurance as determinants.

Research Objectives

This work is specifically designed to:

- i. find out if there is any statistically significant difference in the effect of human competence on customer loyalty compared with AI competence;
- ii. examine the extent to which human responsiveness differs from AI responsiveness in influencing customer loyalty;
- iii. draw a comparison between the level of empathy demonstrated by human agents and that of AI systems in influencing customer loyalty;
- iv. find out the relative impact of human communication versus AI-driven communication on customer loyalty in service interactions;
- v. find out if human-provided assurance and AI-generated assurance differ in impacting customer loyalty.

Research Questions

The following research questions are put forward to guide the study:

- i. To what extent does the impact of human competence on customer loyalty differ from that of AI competence?
- ii. How does human responsiveness differ from AI responsiveness in influencing customer loyalty?
- iii. How does the level of empathy demonstrated by human agents compare to that of AI systems in influencing customer loyalty?
- iv. What is the level of difference between the impact of human communication on customer loyalty and the impact of AI-driven communication on customer loyalty in service interactions?
- v. To what extent does human-provided assurance differ from AI-generated assurance in impacting customer loyalty?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are considered in this work:

Ho1: There is no statistically significant difference in the effect of human competence compared to AI competence on customer loyalty.

Ho1: There is no statistically significant difference in the effect of human responsiveness compared to AI responsiveness on customer loyalty.

Ho2: The effect of human empathy on customer loyalty is not statistically different from the

effect of AI empathy on customer loyalty.

Ho3: The effect of human communication on customer loyalty is not statistically different from the effect of AI communication on customer loyalty.

Ho4: The effect of human assurance on customer loyalty is not significantly different from the effect of AI assurance on customer loyalty.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Humans and Artificial Intelligence

AI is the study of how to produce machines that have some of the qualities that the human mind has, such as the ability to understand language, recognize pictures, solve problems, and learn. AI can be defined as a branch of computer science that aims at developing smart machines capable of performing tasks requiring human intelligence (Bipasha and Aniket, 2020). It is a flourishing phenomenon that is attracting intense interest from the public, companies, and researchers (Suraña and Aramendia, 2024). AI in digital marketing, not only influences marketing strategies, business models, marketing procedures, and consumer service options, but also influences customer behaviour (Rabby et al., 2021).

AI tools are routinely used to analyse customer data and customer products (Jain and Gandhi, 2021). Ifekanandu et al. (2023) posited that AI effectiveness must include the ability to learn from experience, the ability to reason for decision-making, quick responses, and inference power, as well as the ability to make decisions as they relate to priorities and handle complex and ambiguous tasks. While AI automation drives productivity and efficiency, it cannot replace the empathy and connection humans bring to the workplace. However, over-reliance on AI-powered automation is resulting in a lack of human touch, perceived bias, technical issues and errors, and poor feedback systems, making customers feel frustrated and unsatisfied, and leading to a decrease in customer patronage.

On the other hand, human intelligence is unique and inherent. It entails human critical thinking, creativity, empathy and emotional intelligence. This uniqueness is unlike artificial intelligence which is anchored on set rules and algorithms. Companies succeed with AI when they adopt a human-centered approach, offering personalized experiences and fostering strong relationships and customer loyalty. This is because AI doesn't possess the ability to think critically, adapt to new scenarios, and express complex emotions. Therefore, most customers are dissatisfied with the absence of a human touch in contemporary business. According to Singh and Singh (2024), it has been observed that customers tend to have a more pronounced unfavourable attitude toward customer service provided by AI as compared to their human counterparts. Human can tailor interactions to individual customer needs.

Empathy

Empathy is crucial in business. It helps customer service to build positive customer experience and long-term business-customer relationships. Empathy is the ability to share someone's feelings or experiences by imagining what it would be like to be in their situation. It is all about human interaction with a customer. Matan et al. (2024) observed that despite the advancement of AI in generating empathetic responses, humans still place a higher value on empathy than AI. Business organizations with empathy cultivate deeper relationships with their consumers and loyalty. Singha and Singh (2024) opined that giving a better customer experience is apt and generates sustainable growth and success in today's competitive market scenario.

Responsiveness

In business, responsiveness is the ability to react quickly and positively to customers' needs and wants. When a business responds quickly to its customers' problems, trust is built. Currently, most buyers experience trust issues due to AI innovation, and, as a result, clients are keen to spend more time educating themselves before they commit to a purchase (Rabby et al., 2021). The use of chatbots gives quick and accurate responses to queries, reducing the response time and improving customer satisfaction. One of the main issues of debate related to AI is the degree of responsiveness, and several authors emphasized the importance of initial trust in these new technologies (Pelau et al. 2020). Oritsegbemi

(2023) opined that AI can only perform limited tasks, and the level of its functionality depends on the amount of data with which it was programmed.

Communication

Communication is not only a process of transmitting information, ideas, or feelings from one entity to another - it goes beyond that. Communication originated from a Latin word, *communis*, which means to share, to have in common, so when we communicate, we are meant to share, to have something in common. It is a two - way process that ensures that a well encoded message transmitted from a source, gets to the receiver without any interference, and comes back with the right feedback. This is why effective communication is always projected. AI has transformed communication through emerging technologies, enhancing how people interact with machines. Artificial intelligence (AI) and people's interactions with it, through virtual agents, social bots, and language-generation software, do not fit neatly into paradigms of communication theory that have long focused on human-human communication (Andrea and Seth, 2019).

Assurance

One of the critical factors that impacts the success of a business is the assurance that is given to customers. The application of AI has helped to provide customers with a seamless, personalized experience and proactive support. More importantly, the role of humans in building customer assurance cannot be underestimated, as humans help in building personalized customer service and customer-centric culture within the workplace. The current adoption of AI has presented some threats that prompt Nene (2024) to state that machines are not accountable, but we are responsible and accountable. There has been a strong emphasis on improving customer assurance as a means of responding to customers' feedback and complaints. Any business with a keen interest in building customer assurance should establish a strong business-customer relationship. Customers with a high level of assurance are more likely to be loyal and make a repeat purchase.

Customer Loyalty

The concept of customer loyalty is an essential issue in marketing. Customer loyalty is a product of a satisfied customer. To ensure customer satisfaction, companies should understand customer-specific needs and address customer complaints or problems in a friendly manner (Awan and Rehman, 2014). As a matter of fact, according to Andervazh et al. (2013), customer loyalty is a measure of the attachment that a customer has to a brand that brings the firm many benefits. Such benefits are repeat purchases and brand recommendations to friends and relatives. Awan and Rehman (2014) averred that loyal customers may also express their loyalty by giving a greater share of their wallets to their high-valued brands and by generating positive word-of-mouth referrals. It is important to know that, in recent times, most companies are relating and striving to build more direct and lasting relationships with customers.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Researchers (2025)

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Impact of Human and Artificial Intelligence Competencies on Customer Loyalty

Theoretical Review

Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT)

Richard L. Oliver first proposed the expectation confirmation theory in 1980. ECT is a theory that explains consumer satisfaction and repurchase intentions. The theory postulates that customers form expectations of the product they buy and the outcome of their after-purchase evaluation will determine whether they will make a repeat purchase or not. AlSokkar et al. (2024) corroborated when they advised that customers should have fair expectations about the quality of their interactions with e-commerce technology. If expectations are rightly confirmed, repeat purchase can be made. Villarin (2021) and Al-Gasawneh et al. (2022) also opined that a customer's degree of pleasure is directly proportional to how well a product or service meets their expectations. The idea behind this theory is to ensure that businesses promote good communication, deliver accurate information, gather customer feedback, and understand customer expectations.

Empirical Review

Wirtz et al. (2018) conducted a study on empathy and customer loyalty in Human vs. AI-driven customer service. The study aimed at examining the role of empathy in customer service and its influence on customer loyalty, comparing human and AI-driven agents' effectiveness in demonstrating empathy. A mixed-method approach was used in this study. The authors first conducted qualitative interviews with customers to explore their perceptions of empathy in human vs. AI agents. This was followed up with a survey to gather quantitative data from a larger sample.

Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, while the survey responses were subjected to regression analysis to examine the relationship between empathy and customer loyalty. The study found that empathy significantly impacted customer loyalty, with human agents outpacing AI in emotional

engagement. However, AI-driven systems that utilized advanced natural language processing (NLP) techniques were able to simulate empathetic responses, leading to improved customer perceptions.

Van et al. (2010) conducted a research study on responsiveness and the role of AI in enhancing customer loyalty. The study aimed at exploring the relationship between responsiveness in customer service interactions and customer loyalty, particularly examining the role of AI and human agents in fostering responsiveness. The authors conducted a longitudinal survey across different service industries to evaluate the responsiveness of both human and AI agents. Customers were asked to rate their experiences based on the speed and effectiveness of the service they received. The data were analyzed using structural equation modeling (SEM) to understand the impact of responsiveness on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The study found that responsiveness was a significant determinant of customer satisfaction, with AI systems providing faster responses. However, human agents were preferred for more complex, nuanced inquiries. The quick response time of AI was associated with increased loyalty in high-volume service environments.

Lemon and Verhoef (2016) conducted a study on communication and assurance in hybrid customer service models. The study aimed at investigating how communication and assurance in hybrid service models (involving both AI and human agents) contribute to customer loyalty. The authors conducted a comparative analysis of hybrid service models in retail and telecommunications sectors. They used customer satisfaction surveys and in-depth interviews to collect data on customer perceptions of communication and assurance. The collected data were analyzed using content analysis for qualitative insights and regression analysis for understanding the correlation between communication, assurance, and customer loyalty. The study found that clear and consistent communication was essential for building customer trust and loyalty. AI systems were praised for providing consistent and accurate information, while human agents excelled in fostering personal connections and resolving complex issues.

Chung et al. (2019) carried a research work on the Impact of human vs. AI competencies on service quality and loyalty. This study aimed at comparing the impact of human and AI competencies on service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty in online retail settings. The authors conducted an experimental study where participants interacted with both AI-driven and human agents across different customer service scenarios (transactional vs. complex inquiries). They measured customer satisfaction and loyalty through pre and post-interaction surveys. The data were analyzed using ANOVA and regression analysis to identify significant differences in service quality perceptions and their influence on loyalty between human and AI interactions. The study found that human agents were more effective in handling complex service issues, promoting long-term loyalty through personalized service. In contrast, AI agents were more efficient and consistent in resolving transactional queries, which led to higher short-term satisfaction but less impact on long-term loyalty.

Gap in Literature

Existing research has extensively examined the individual competencies of human and AI agents in customer service, yet there is still a notable gap in comparative studies that assess how these competencies collectively influence customer loyalty. However, empirical analyses directly comparing these competencies and their impact on customer loyalty are limited. Furthermore, studies have highlighted that AI agents, despite advancements, often fall short in replicating the emotional and social dimensions of human interactions, which are crucial for building customer loyalty. This underscores the need for research that not only compares human and AI competencies but also explores how their integration can enhance customer loyalty. Additionally, while the importance of empathy in customer service is well-documented, there is no consensus on the effectiveness of AI in delivering empathetic responses. Some studies suggest that AI can exhibit empathy comparable to human agents, while others argue that AI lacks the genuine emotional understanding that human agents provide. This disparity indicates a need for further investigation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study on the impact of human and artificial intelligence competencies on customer satisfaction used empathy, responsiveness, communication, and assurance as determinants. For each of the hypotheses formulated earlier, we aimed at measuring the differences in human and AI competencies along these variables and identifying areas where each option is lagging behind or doing better.

A cross-sectional survey research design method was adopted, and the primary data collection method was used for collecting the data subsequently used for analysis in this study. Knowing that the population elements (customers) are infinite, the researchers used the Cochran method of sample size determination to determine a sample size of three hundred and sixty-nine (369). A stratified sampling approach was adopted (only enlightened customers of various products, who are on WhatsApp were used). A four-point Likert scale structure was used in designing the questionnaire that was administered on the said respondents. These questionnaires were conveniently self-administered on the respondents, who in turn completed and returned all electronically using WhatsApp. With the aid of SPSS, multiple linear regression and independent samples t-test were used for the analysis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Regression results of Human and AI competencies impact on customer loyalty

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		t	P-value (2-tailed)
	B	Std. Error		
(Constant)	9.820	0.821	11.958	< 0.000
Human Competence	0.082	0.022	3.690	0.003
AI Competence	0.056	0.021	2.695	0.007

Source: Researchers (2025)

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table 1 gives the results of the multiple linear regression analysis done to examine the influence of Human Competence and AI Competence on Customer Loyalty. The regression model included both variables as predictors of customer loyalty. Human competence showed a positive and statistically significant relationship with customer loyalty, with a regression coefficient (B) of 0.082, standard error of 0.022, a t-value of 3.690, and a p-value of 0.003. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the result is statistically significant. This means that an increase in human competence is associated with a meaningful increase in customer loyalty. It suggests that human service agents play a critical role in shaping positive customer experiences that lead to loyalty.

AI competence also had a positive and statistically significant effect on customer loyalty, with a coefficient (B) of 0.056, standard error of 0.021, a t-value of 2.695, and a p-value of 0.007. Though the magnitude of the coefficient is slightly lower than that of human competence, its statistical significance indicates that AI capabilities also contribute meaningfully to customer loyalty. The constant of the model is 9.820 with a t-value of 11.958 and p-value of 0.000, indicating a statistically significant base level of customer loyalty when both human and AI competencies are zero. This implies that other unmeasured factors may also contribute to loyalty but are not included in this model.

Both human and AI competencies significantly and positively influence customer loyalty. However, human competence has a slightly stronger effect based on the regression coefficient. This underscores the importance of maintaining high human service standards even as AI adoption increases. Organizations are encouraged to pursue a complementary strategy, enhancing human capabilities while investing in AI development, to maximize customer satisfaction and loyalty outcomes.

Table 2: Independent Samples T Test for Equality of Means of Human and AI on competence variables

Variable	Mean of Human	Mean of AI	Mean Difference	Std. Error of Mean Difference	t	df	P-value (2-tailed)
Responsiveness	8.098	9.645	-1.547	0.1465	-10.558	736	< 0.001
Empathy	9.892	8.72	1.173	0.1076	10.898	736	< 0.001
Communication	8.827	9.548	-0.721	0.1393	-5.1756	736	< 0.001
Assurance	9.507	8.667	0.840	0.1257	6.682	736	< 0.001

Table 2 gives the results of the Independent Samples T-Test conducted to compare perceptions of Human and Artificial Intelligence (AI) competence across the four key service quality variables: Responsiveness, Empathy, Communication, and Assurance. The analysis revealed statistically significant differences across all four variables, indicating that participants perceived differences in competence between humans and AI in each area. The mean difference for responsiveness was -1.547 with a standard error of 0.1465, yielding a t-value of -10.558 and a p-value < 0.001. This result is statistically significant, indicating that AI agents were rated significantly more responsive than human agents in responding to queries and suggesting solutions to customers. The negative mean difference shows that responsiveness scores were higher for AI and this corroborates with the study conducted by Van (2010).

In the empathy domain, the mean difference was 1.173, with a standard error of 0.1076, a t-value of 10.898, and a p-value < 0.001. The positive mean difference indicates that human agents were perceived to exhibit greater empathy than AI systems in this study. This supports the position of Matan et al. (2024) that made it clear that humans still place a higher value on empathy than AI despite the advancement of AI in generating empathetic responses. Similarly, Oritsegbemi (2023) emphasized the enduring superiority of humans as the higher class of beings, particularly in domains requiring emotional intelligence and moral judgment. These align with the findings of the current study, which underscore the continued relevance of human agents in delivering empathetic-driven customer service interactions - a major area where AI systems currently fall short.

Communication showed a mean difference of -0.721, standard error of 0.1393, a t-value of -5.1756, and a p-value < 0.001. This statistically significant result indicates that AI systems were rated higher in communication competence than human agents. Despite the engagement of communications experts by most firms, their performances cannot be equated with that of AI.

For assurance, the mean difference was 0.840, with a standard error of 0.1257, a t-value of 6.682, and a p-value < 0.001. This statistically significant positive difference suggests that human agents were perceived to offer greater assurance than AI systems.

All four competence variables demonstrated statistically significant differences between Human agents and AI systems. AI systems were perceived to outperform human agents in responsiveness and communication, while human agents were perceived as more competent in empathy and assurance than AI systems. This analysis offers useful implications for organizations seeking to balance AI integration with human support, emphasizing the need for a hybrid model that leverages the unique strengths of both.

CONCLUSION

This study has demonstrated that both human and artificial intelligence (AI) competencies significantly influence customer loyalty, though their strengths vary across different service dimensions. Human agents were found to excel in empathy and assurance, fostering stronger emotional connections and trust with customers. Conversely, AI systems showed superior performance in responsiveness and communication, offering efficient and consistent interactions. These findings highlight that while AI technologies are

becoming increasingly proficient in handling customer interactions, the human touch remains indispensable in areas requiring emotional intelligence and personalized assurance. Therefore, a balanced integration of human and AI capabilities is essential for enhancing overall customer loyalty.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Integrate Human-AI Collaboration. Organizations should not view human and AI agents as substitutes, but as complementary forces. A hybrid model that leverages the emotional intelligence of humans and the efficiency of AI should be prioritized.
2. Invest in AI Development. Continuous investment in AI technology is crucial to further enhance its responsiveness and communication abilities, making it a reliable first-contact solution for routine customer inquiries.
3. Human Agent Training. Regular training programs should be implemented for human agents, focusing on improving responsiveness, emotional engagement, and problem-solving skills, to complement the strengths of AI.
4. Context-Based Deployment. Companies should adopt a context-driven approach, assigning AI to handle time-sensitive and routine queries, while reserving complex and emotionally charged interactions for human agents.
5. Monitor and Evaluate Performance. Ongoing assessment of both human and AI performance in customer service should be conducted to ensure continuous improvement and to adapt strategies based on evolving customer expectations.

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Please, complete the questionnaire accordingly.

Key: SD = Strongly Disagree D = Disagree A= Agree SA = Strongly Agree

		SD	D	A	SA
1a	Human Responsiveness				
i	The human representative responded to my request in a timely manner.				
ii	The human representative prioritized my issue and took immediate steps to resolve it.				
iii	The human representative was quick to provide a solution to my problem.				
1b	AI Responsiveness				
i	The AI system responded to my request in a timely manner.				
ii	The AI representative prioritized my issue and took immediate steps to resolve it.				
iii	The AI system was quick to provide a solution to my problem.				
2a	Human Empathy				
i	The human representative showed genuine concern for my needs.				
ii	The human representative understood my situation and made me feel heard.				
iii	The human representative was compassionate while addressing my issue.				
2b	AI Empathy				
i	The AI system showed a sense of understanding of my needs.				
ii	The AI system responded in a way that made me feel heard and understood.				
iii	The AI system was designed in a way that conveyed care while resolving my issue.				
3a	Human Communication				
i	The human representative communicated clearly and effectively.				
ii	The human representative explained the solution in a way that was easy to understand.				
iii	The human representative ensured I understood the next steps in the process.				
3b	AI Communication				
i	The AI system communicated clearly and effectively.				
ii	The AI system explained the solution in a way that was easy to understand.				
iii	The AI system explained the solution in a way that was easy to understand.				
4a	Human Assurance				
i	I felt confident in the human representative's ability to resolve my issue.				
ii	The human representative assured me that my issue would be solved.				
iii	The human representative provided me with a sense of trust and security.				
4b	AI Assurance				
i	I felt confident in the AI system's ability to resolve my issue.				
ii	The AI system assured me that my issue would be solved.				
iii	The AI system provided me with a sense of trust and security.				
	Customer Loyalty				
i	I will continue using the channel if I am satisfied with their services.				
ii	I will recommend the channel to friends and family.				
iii	The channel will be my first choice when I have a complaint to make.				